

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for PARP-1 (P09874) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and flow cytometry

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Abstract

Poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase-1 (PARP-1) is a nuclear enzyme that plays a central role in DNA damage detection and repair, but growing evidence highlights its broader influence on neuronal function and vulnerability. Here we have characterized twenty-five PARP-1 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence, and twenty-four antibodies for flow cytometry using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID P09874, *PARP1*, PARP-1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence, flow cytometry

Introduction

In the central nervous system, PARP-1 activity is tightly regulated to maintain genomic integrity under physiological conditions; however, excessive activation following oxidative or excitotoxic stress triggers energy depletion, impaired mitochondrial function, and a form of programmed cell death termed parthanatos [1]. Dysregulated PARP-1 signaling has been implicated in a range of neurodegenerative disorders, including Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, where chronic inflammation and mitochondrial dysfunction converge on PARP-1-dependent pathways [2]. Recent work also suggests that PARP-1 modulates chromatin accessibility and transcriptional programs relevant to synaptic plasticity, neuroinflammation, and glial responses [3].

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data [4]. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein [4]. Here we characterized twenty-five commercial PARP-1 antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence, and twenty-four commercial antibodies in flow cytometry. Antibodies were selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence (also referred to as immunocytochemistry), and flow cytometry enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of PARP-1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway [5] and in Table 5 of this data note [4].

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells [6, 7]. The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off [8]. PARP-1 is an abundant and ubiquitously expressed protein across many cancer cell lines. The HAP1 expresses the *PARP1* transcript at $7.8 \log_2$ TPM+1, and a *PARP1* KO HAP1 cell line was obtained from Horizon Discovery (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the HAP1 does not carry mutations in the

PARP1 that could affect antibody–epitope binding. A HEK293T KO cell line is also available at Abcam (Table 1) and was tested in this study.

We first compared the expression of PARP-1 by western blot in the two KO cell lines side-by-side and using three different antibodies (Figure 1A). We then screened all remaining twenty-two by western blot using HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO protein lysates (Figure 1B). Samples were run on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all PARP-1 antibodies (Table 2) in parallel.

We then assessed the capability of the twenty-five antibodies to capture PARP-1 from HAP1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific PARP-1 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, twenty-five antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the PARP-1 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis [4].

For flow cytometry, HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilized and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Twenty-four PARP-1 antibodies (Table 3) were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 4.

In conclusion, we have screened twenty-five PARP-1 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence and twenty-four commercial antibodies by flow cytometry by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 5 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications [8]. High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect PARP-1 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study PARP-1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available PARP-1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in PARP-1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. PARP-1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) [4]. Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. Primary antibodies used in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are listed in Table 2. Primary antibodies used in flow cytometry in Table 3, and secondary antibodies are listed in Table 4. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) [9, 10]. All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). All tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary PARP-1 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.94 air objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification [12]. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were detached, and five million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were then centrifuged at 300 x *g* for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). Cell populations were then combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 μ L of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilised in 400 μ L PBS with 0.1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J63521) for 10 minutes at room temperature, centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150 μ L of 1% BSA PBS with PARP-1 primary antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500 μ L of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies (0.83 μ g/ml) in 150 μ L of 1% BSA PBS for 30 minutes on ice. 500 μ L of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C.

Tubes were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, within that gate single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H and then KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the PARP-1 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HD HAP1-64504	NA	HAP1	<i>PARP1</i> KO
Abcam	ab255449	CVCL_0063	HEK293T	WT
Abcam	ab266598	CVCL_B3DF	HEK293T	<i>PARP1</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the PARP-1 antibodies tested in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab191217**	1016677-48	AB_2861274	recombinant mono	EPR18461	rabbit	0.832	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab32071**	GR3369201-3	AB_777100	recombinant mono	E78	rabbit	0.095	Wb
Abcam	ab32138**	1091350-2	AB_777101	recombinant mono	E102	rabbit	0.105	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab32378**	1110701-1	AB_2236739	recombinant mono	Y17	rabbit	0.522	Wb
ABclonal	A0010	3560363007	AB_2756887	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.650	Wb, IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP33754_T100	QC72848-20190621	AB_842407	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP74915_P050	QC46300	AB_3698303	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.500	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-26439**	N0117W	AB_3638628	recombinant mono	8C7	rabbit	0.275	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB8095*	CHRL0121121	AB_3659025	monoclonal	839120	mouse	0.500	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	9532**	10	AB_659884	recombinant mono	46D11	rabbit	0.438	Wb, IP
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	AFFN-PARP1-17B10*	AFFN-PARP1-17B10	AB_2617801	monoclonal	AFFN-PARP1-17B10	mouse	0.016	other
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	CPTC-PARP1-2**	9/7-23	AB_2943572	recombinant mono	CPTC-PARP1-2	rabbit	0.009	NA
GeneTex	GTX100573	42712	AB_1241155	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.300	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX112839	40961	AB_10728612	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX112864	45574	AB_11173565	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.100	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX132329	42347	AB_2886614	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.330	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX628836*	44888	AB_2888062	monoclonal	GT6212	mouse	1.000	Wb, IP
GeneTex	GTX632388*	42086	AB_2888311	monoclonal	GT982	mouse	1.650	Wb, IP, IF

GeneTex	GTX636804**	44711	AB_3698335	recombinant mono	HL1364	rabbit	1.500	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX636805**	44683	AB_3698336	recombinant mono	HL1365	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IF
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1544**	RA2001012	AB_3698365	recombinant mono	2G13	rabbit	0.030	Wb
MilliporeSigma	ZRB1545**	RA2001013	AB_3698366	recombinant mono	12N17	rabbit	0.030	Wb
Proteintech	13371-1-AP	00176478	AB_2160459	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.500	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	66520-1-Ig*	10025840	AB_2881883	monoclonal	1D7D4	mouse	0.500	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-41125**	AC4649689 B	AB_2898879	recombinant mono	SU03-68	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Summary of the PARP-1 antibodies tested in flow cytometry

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab191217**	1117423-4	AB_2861274	recombinant mono	EPR18461	Rabbit	0.733	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab32071**	1029023-6	AB_777100	recombinant mono	E78	Rabbit	0.095	Wb
Abcam	ab32138**	1091350-4	AB_777101	recombinant mono	E102	Rabbit	0.105	Wb, IF, FC (Intra)
Abcam	ab32378**	1110701-4	AB_2236739	recombinant mono	Y17	Rabbit	0.522	Wb
ABclonal	A27791**	6100008674		recombinant mono	-	Rabbit	1.170	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP33754-T100	QC46300	AB_842407	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.500	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP74915-P050	QC72848-20190621	AB_3698303	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.500	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	9532**	10	AB_659884	recombinant mono	46D11	Rabbit	0.438	Wb, IP
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	AFFN-PARP1-17B10*	4-18-19	AB_2617801	monoclonal	AFFN-PARP1-17B10	Mouse	0.031	Wb
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank (DSHB)	CPTC-PARP1-2*	09-07-23	AB_2943572	monoclonal	CPTC-PARP1-2	Rabbit	0.018	NA
GeneTex	GTX100573	42712	AB_1241155	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.300	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX112839	40961	AB_10728612	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	1.000	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX112864	45574	AB_11173565	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.100	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX132329	42347	AB_2886614	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	1.330	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX628836*	44888	AB_2888062	monoclonal	GT6212	Mouse	1.000	Wb, IP
GeneTex	GTX632388*	42086	AB_2888311	monoclonal	GT982	Mouse	1.650	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX636804**	44711	AB_3698335	recombinant mono	HL1364	Rabbit	1.500	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX636805**	44683	AB_3698336	recombinant mono	HL1365	Rabbit	1.000	Wb, IF
Proteintech	13371-1-AP	00153210	AB_2160459	polyclonal	-	Rabbit	0.500	Wb, IP, IF, FC (intra)
Proteintech	66520-1-Ig*	10025840	AB_2881883	monoclonal	1D7D4	Mouse	0.500	Wb, IP, IF, FC (intra)
R&D Systems	MAB8095*	CHRL0124041	AB_3659025	monoclonal	839120	Mouse	0.500	Wb

Sigma-Aldrich	ZRB1545**	RA2001013	AB_3698366	recombinant mono	12N17	Rabbit	0.030	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	14-6667-82*	3000506	AB_10698017	monoclonal	HC2R8	Mouse	0.500	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-41125**	79636061	AB_2898879	recombinant mono	SU03-68	Rabbit	1.000	Wb, IF, FC

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation; FC = flow cytometry, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM003	AB_3068539	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 647-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.83
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 647-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.83

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and flow cytometry

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Figure 1: PARP-1 antibody screening by western blot (1/2)

B. Screening in HAP1 (continued)

Figure 1: PARP-1 antibody screening by western blot (2/2)

Figure 2: PARP-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (1/2)

Figure 2: PARP-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/2)

Figure 3: PARP1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: PARP1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

Figure 4: PARP-1 antibody screening by flow cytometry (1/2)

Figure 4: PARP-1 antibody screening by flow cytometry (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: PARP-1 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates from HEK293T and HAP1 (WT and *PARP1* KO) cells were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed in western blot with the three indicated PARP-1 antibodies. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab191217** at 1/1000; 9532** at 1/1000; ZRB1545** at 1/500. **B)** 30 µg of HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO lysates were processed for western blot with the remaining PARP-1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab32071** at 1/1000; ab32138** at 1/5000; ab32378** at 1/1000; A0010 at 1/500; ARP33754_T100 at 1/200; ARP74915_P050 at 1/250; NBP3-26439** at 1/2000 ; MAB8095* at 1/500; AFFN-PARP1-17B10* at 1/500; CPTC-PARP1-2** at 1/50; GTX100573 at 1/1000; GTX112839 at 1/1000; GTX112864 at 1/5000; GTX132329 at 1/1000; GTX628836* at 1/1000; GTX632388* at 1/1000; GTX636804** at 1/10 000; GTX636805** at 1/10 000; ZRB1544** at 1/500; 13371-1-AP at 1/2000; 66520-1-Ig* at 1/10000; MA5-41125** at 1/2000. Predicted band size: 113 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: PARP-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated PARP-1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the PARP-1 antibody ab191217** used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitated. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: PARP-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated PARP-1 antibodies and with the corresponding fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: : ab191217** at 1/800; ab32071** at 1/50; ab32138** at 1/50; ab32378** at 1/500; A0010 at 1/100; ARP33754_T100 at 1/1000; ARP74915_P050 at 1/500; NBP3-26439** at 1/300 ; MAB8095* at 1/250; 9532** at 1/200; AFFN-PARP1-17B10* at 1/20; CPTC-PARP1-2** at 1/10; GTX100573 at 1/300;

GTX112839 at 1/500; GTX112864 at 1/500; GTX132329 at 1/1000; GTX628836* at 1/500; GTX632388* at 1/400; GTX636804** at 1/500; GTX636805** at 1/500; ZRB1544** at 1/30; ZRB1545** at 1/30; 13371-1-AP at 1/200; 66520-1-Ig* at 1/200; MA5-41125** at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: PARP-1 antibody screening by flow cytometry.

HAP1 WT and *PARP1* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% Triton X-100. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated PARP-1 antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. Antibody dilutions used: ab191217** at 1/7330, ab32071** at 1/950, ab32138** at 1/1050, ab32378** at 1/5220, A27791** at 1/11700, ARP74915-P050 at 1/5000, ARP33754-T100 at 1/5000, 9532** at 1/4380, AFFN-PARP1-17B10* at 1/31, CPTC-PARP1-2* at 1/180, GTX100573 at 1/3000, GTX112839 at 1/10000, GTX112864 at 1/1000, GTX132329 at 1/13300, GTX628836* at 1/10000, GTX632388* at 1/16500, GTX636804** at 1/15000, GTX636805** at 1/10000, 13371-1-AP at 1/5000, 66520-1-Ig* at 1/5000, MAB8095* at 1/5000, ZRB1545** at 1/300, 14-6667-82* at 1/5000, MA5-41125** at 1/10000. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.